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High-resolution surface soil moisture retrieval: A hybrid machine learning framework integrating change detection and downscaling for precision water management

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ABSTRACT

Soil moisture (SM) is vital for comprehending the hydrological cycle and managing climatic extremes. Fine-scale accurate SM products hold more and more significant value to water management and precise agricultural irrigation. While in-situ measurements provide high accuracy, their limited spatial coverage and high costs necessitate alternative approaches. Remote sensing enables large-scale monitoring; however, satellite-based SM products have relatively lower spatial resolution, making them less suitable for practical applications. This study presents an innovative high-resolution surface soil moisture (SSM) retrieval framework combining machine learning (ML), change detection and downscaling (CD-DS) methods. The procedure is applied over Catalonia, Spain. The framework integrates Sentinel-1 SAR, Sentinel-2 normalized difference vegetation indices (NDVI), and DISPATCH background SSM data to generate 30-m resolution SSM. A novel backscatter difference variable, derived from the change detection method, improves model performance by addressing vegetation. The ML model was trained using in-situ SSM data collected from 2017 to 2021 and validated against independent in-situ measurement datasets. Among the evaluated algorithms, XGBoost model performed best, achieving an R^2 of 0.933 and RMSE of $0.023 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Validation with ground measurements with different landcover types showed an average correlation of 0.63, a ubRMSE of $0.045 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, and minimal bias of $0.024 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Notably, backscatter difference emerged as the second most important variable in the ML model after background SSM, highlighting its significance in improving SSM retrieval accuracy. Comparisons with data from 54 measurement sites, obtained during a 2015 field campaign, yielded an R value of 0.82, a RMSE of $0.06 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Temporal analysis revealed strong consistency with in-situ data, capturing seasonal trends and abrupt changes after precipitation and irrigation events. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of SSM is closely aligned with irrigation type maps, showing higher SSM values in irrigated areas and lower values in rainfed regions. This approach delivers precise field-scale SSM estimates, making it a valuable tool for drought monitoring and modern agricultural practices.

1. Introduction

Soil moisture (SM) serves as a key parameter in agriculture and water management, influencing irrigation, drought assessment, crop yield, and rainfall modelling (Gaona et al., 2022). Seasonally, it affects wildfire spread, evaporation, and plant growth in summer, while in winter, it plays a role in carbon storage and vegetation dynamics (Gu et al., 2019).

SM is measured through in-situ sampling or remote sensing (Peng

et al., 2017). In-situ methods offer high accuracy but are costly, have limited spatial coverage, and may cause environmental disturbances during sampling (Arabi et al., 2020). Remote sensing allows for large-scale monitoring but is constrained by factors such as resolution, weather conditions, and model accuracy (Abbaszadeh et al., 2019; Das et al., 2019). To enhance reliability, many studies integrate both approaches, using in-situ data—such as those provided by global ground networks like the International Soil Moisture Network (ISMN)—for the

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calibration and validation (Arabi et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2024).

Among remote sensing techniques, optical remote sensing is widely used for SM retrieval due to its high spatial resolution, relying on variables like vegetation indices and surface characteristics to infer SM (Li et al., 2021). While effective in cloud-free conditions, its accuracy declines with cloud cover, aerosols, and dense vegetation, which obscure surface signals (Tao et al., 2019). Moreover, optical sensors do not directly measure SM; instead, they rely on indirect correlations with surface conditions, which may introduce uncertainties. Despite these limitations, optical remote sensing remains valuable when integrated with other data sources to enhance SM retrieval accuracy (Attarzadeh et al., 2018).

Several recent Earth observation satellites, such as the Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) and Sentinel-1 are equipped with microwave sensors, enabling them to perform microwave remote sensing, which is subdivided into passive and active methods (Fan et al., 2018). Unlike optical sensors, passive microwave remote sensing directly measures soil microwave emissions, which are highly sensitive to moisture content (Tao et al., 2019). Passive microwave sensors offer wide-area coverage, short revisit periods, and high sensitivity to SM variations, making them well-suited for large-scale studies. However, a major limitation is their coarse spatial resolution, which restricts their applicability in fine-scale studies (Das et al., 2019).

To overcome this limitation, downscaling techniques have been developed to enhance passive microwave SM products' spatial resolution (Senanayake et al., 2024). These approaches integrate multi-source datasets—including optical indices (e.g., NDVI), meteorological information (e.g., temperature, precipitation) and terrain information (e.g., slope)—to refine SM estimates at finer spatial scales (Huang et al., 2022). For example, Chen et al. (2019) downscaled AMSR-E SM data from 25 km to 1 km using random forest and Cubist algorithms, incorporating digital elevation model and NDVI as key environmental variables. Similarly, Abowarda et al. (2021) incorporated MODIS, Landsat, multiple background SSM products, soil texture, surface temperature, and albedo into ML models to generate a 30-m resolution SM dataset with high accuracy ($R = 0.70\text{--}0.84$, $RMSE = 0.031\text{--}0.050\text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$).

In general, the inclusion of high-quality auxiliary data—particularly vegetation indices, temperature, and soil characteristics—improves the accuracy of SM estimation. However, the mismatch in spatial resolution or limited availability of such auxiliary datasets can present challenges for implementing SM downscaling at fine spatial scales.

Active microwave remote sensing, especially Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), has gained attention for SM retrieval due to its high spatial resolution and all-weather capability (Zhu et al., 2023). Compared to passive microwave techniques, SAR provides finer spatial detail, with L-band penetrating up to ~ 5 cm and C-band ~ 2 cm. However, surface roughness and vegetation complicate retrieval, requiring robust correction models (Atun et al., 2024). To improve accuracy, researchers integrate SAR with optical data using multi-source fusion techniques (Dorigo et al., 2015; Peng et al., 2017). Recent studies demonstrate promising results: Efremova et al. (2022) used Sentinel-1/-2 data and a gap-filling method combined with random forest to estimate SM in vineyards, achieving $R^2 = 0.89$ and $RMSE = 0.045\text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, though challenges remain regarding generalizability across crop types. Meanwhile, Inoubli et al. (2024) assessed various surface scattering models within the Water Cloud Model using Sentinel-1 VV/VH and Sentinel-2 NDVI over maize fields, showing that models offer good sensitivity to SM (unbiased root mean squared difference (ubRMSD) = 0.295 dB). While ML based downscaling improves resolution, further efforts are needed to develop adaptable, physically consistent, and cost-effective SM retrieval methods suitable for diverse agricultural environments.

One particularly promising technique in SAR-based SM retrieval is Change Detection (CD), which leverages multi-temporal SAR data to track SM variations (Xu et al., 2024). Change detection techniques in SAR remote sensing have become increasingly valuable for SM retrieval (Du et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2017; Zribi et al., 2014). It is

a method that identifies surface changes by comparing SAR images from different time intervals. Specifically, the differences at various time points are used to obtain the parameters of a polynomial. By analysing temporal variations between consecutive dates in SAR backscatter signals and fitting this polynomial, SM can be estimated (Gao et al., 2017). This method leverages the sensitivity of SAR to vegetation and dielectric properties, which are influenced by SM levels. The CD method allows for the differentiation between wet and dry soil conditions, providing a dynamic and continuous assessment of SM. Integrating multi-temporal SAR data improves the accuracy of SM retrieval by reducing the effects of surface roughness and vegetation cover. Gao et al. (2017) applied two distinct CD methods to process Sentinel-1 data, enhancing the inversion process through frequent observations and radar signal differences derived from the NDVI optical index, validating one year and half of satellite data, resulting in volumetric moisture RMS errors of $0.087\text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$ and $0.059\text{ m}^3/\text{m}^3$, respectively. Zhu et al. (2022) proposed an advanced change detection (ACD) method for improved SM retrieval from Sentinel-1 data, which approximates the effect of temporal vegetation variation and applies a temporal SM constraint, resulting in improved correlation coefficient and reduced RMSE and ubRMSE at various scales. The change detection method is predominantly effective for estimating SSM in regions with homogeneous surface types, but shows reduced efficacy in areas with complex terrain and diverse surface types. Furthermore, obtaining absolute SM values using change detection methods necessitates supplementary data to determine SM under the driest and wettest conditions (Du et al., 2024). Given the computational intensity and high data requirements, CD methods remain challenging for large-scale applications, necessitating further advancements in algorithm efficiency and data fusion techniques.

In this study, our goal is to develop a novel approach for generating high spatial resolution SSM, which is applied to the Catalonia region, tailored to practical agricultural applications. Leveraging ML, we innovatively integrate CD into the model framework. This approach enables us to capture the nonlinear relationships among features from different sources, facilitating the retrieval of SM. Specifically, we utilize the VV polarization from Sentinel-1 and the NDVI from Sentinel-2 to calculate backscatter difference. This approach effectively reduces the influence of surface vegetation components and surface roughness. The 1-km DISPATCH SSM is used as the downscaling background SSM value, while in-situ SM measurements serve as labelled data for ML training. This research provides the following key contributions. Firstly, we innovatively incorporate backscatter difference into the downscaling model as a CD variable, introducing a critical input parameter to enhance SSM retrieval accuracy. Secondly, we test four different ML models and identify the most suitable model for high-resolution SSM retrieval. Thirdly, we analyze the contributions of various parameters during model training and identify variables that are highly correlated with SSM. Finally, we achieve high-precision retrieval of SSM at a 30-m resolution, providing valuable insights to support decision-making for field-scale agricultural production activities.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the study area and data sources. The methodology, including data preprocessing, backscatter difference calculation, ML model training, and validation strategies, is presented in Section 3. Section 4 outlines the results, evaluating background SM products, model performance, and validation of retrieved SSM. Section 5 discusses key findings, limitations, and potential improvements. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Study area and materials

2.1. Study area

Catalonia, located on the Iberian Peninsula, is a significant hotspot for climate change and serves as the primary study area. It has a Mediterranean climate with hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters,

Table 1
Datasets used to develop the downscaling SSM retrieval framework.

Category	Data set	Variable	Temporal resolution	Spatial resolution
Satellite Data	Sentinel-1	VV,VH Polarization	Every 6 days	10 m
	Sentinel-2	NDVI	Every 5 days	10 m
Ground-based Data	Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya (ICGC) Soil Monitoring Network	SSM (5 cm depth)	Every 30 min	Points
	H2020 REC Project Field Measurements	SSM (3–5 cm depth)	Every 30 min	Points
Ancillary Data	Sistema de Informació Geogràfica de Parcelas Agrícolas (SIGPAC)	Irrigation status	Annually	Parcel
Remotely Sensed SSM Products	DISPATCH SSM	SSM	Daily	1 km
	Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS) SSM	SSM	Daily	1 km

experiencing periodic droughts that significantly impact agriculture and water resources (Barrera-Escoda and Llasat, 2015). To address water scarcity, the region has adopted conservation strategies, including drip irrigation, precision agriculture, and water-efficient crops (van Hateren et al., 2019). Its rich geoinformation—covering temperature, precipitation, crop types, and irrigation data—provides a strong basis for research on SM.

2.2. Data sets

The datasets of this study are all displayed in Table 1, mainly including satellite remotely sensed data, ground-based data and auxiliary data.

2.2.1. Remotely sensed products

Sentinel-1A, launched in April 2014, and its twin Sentinel-1B feature C-band SAR with VV and VH polarizations, providing 10-meter spatial resolution and a 12-day revisit cycle per satellite. When both were operational, the global temporal resolution improved to 6 days. In this study, Sentinel-1 data were sourced from Google Earth Engine (GEE). All acquisitions were in Interferometric Wide (IW) swath mode, covering incidence angles from approximately 29° to 46°, depending on sub-swath and range position. Both ascending and descending orbit data were used to enhance temporal coverage.

Fig. 1. Study area and major land cover types in the Catalonia region based on SIGPAC (Geographic Information System of Agricultural Plots), including the distribution of in-situ sites and extra validation sites: (a) sampling points from the 2015 Urgell field campaign; (b) Foradada site; (c) Algerri-Balaguer 3 and 4 sites.

Fig. 2. Sites with different land cover types. (a) Clarella site, land cover type: forest; (b) Ribera de Sió site, land cover type: vineyard; (c) Pessonada site, land cover type: forest; (d) Los Coscolls site, land cover type: fruit trees; (e) Batlliu de Sort site, land cover type: forest; (f) Serra de Costa Ampla site, land cover type: shrubs; (Image from ICGC, <https://visors.icgc.cat/mesurasols/>).

Fig. 3. Time span and landcover type of all stations of the ICGC Soil Measurement Network from their commissioning to January 1, 2024.

Sentinel-2, launched in June 2015, carries an MSI sensor with 13 spectral bands. Its visible and near-infrared bands offer 10-meter resolution with a 5-day revisit time. We used Sentinel-2 Level 2A data from GEE, selecting images with <10 % cloud cover. NDVI was calculated using the red and near-infrared bands, generating cloud-free images essential for vegetation monitoring and backscatter difference calculations. This study utilizes data spanning 2017–2024.

2.2.2. Background SM products

The Copernicus Global Land Service (CGLS) SSM1km Version 1.1.1 product is available for the European continent every 3–8 days from January 2015 to October 2016 and daily from October 2016 onward. The original NetCDF file format of the full coverage area across Europe can be obtained from <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/soil-moisture/>.

The Disaggregation based on Physical And Theoretical scale Change (DISPATCH) is another example of fusing optical/thermal LST and vegetation indices to enhance the spatial resolution of passive SM (Merlin et al., 2013). The DISPATCH SSM product used in this study offers a 1-km spatial resolution and a daily temporal resolution, covering the entire Catalonia region.

2.2.3. Ground-based measurements datasets

The ground-based measurement datasets used for accuracy verification come from the Soil Measurement Network of the Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya (ICGC), part of the Catalonia Soil Physical Parameter Monitoring Network (XMS-Cat). Initiated in 2015, this network provides continuous SM and temperature measurements at depths of 5–100 cm across Catalonia (Fig. 1). Data are collected every 30 min along with other environmental parameters to support climate

Fig. 4. Flowchart for generating 30 m CD-DS SSM in this study.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of different background SSM data against ground-based SSM measurements.

Fig. 6. Temporal variations of the different background SSM (DISPATCH SSM, CGLS SSM) and in-situ SSM during 2017 to 2019 at site Ribera de Sió.

Fig. 7. Validation accuracy of the different ML models trained using test samples. (a) XGBoost model, (b) LSTM model, (c) RF model, and (d) SVR model.

assessment and hydrological research. According to the ICGC, stations are primarily located in vineyards at various elevations to monitor long-term soil and environmental changes in this economically significant crop. Most stations are situated on flat or gently sloping terrain, with only a few located in more complex topographic settings. However, visual interpretation indicates that many are positioned at field borders surrounded by shrubs, grass, or trees (Fig. 2). In total, 18 ICGC in-situ stations are used in this study: 13 stations contributed data for model training (2017–2021), while all 18 are used for validation (2022–2024). The remaining 5 stations only became available after 2022 and are thus reserved for the independent validation.

We also utilized validation field data from the H2020 REC project

(“Root Zone SM Estimates at the Daily and Agricultural Field Scales for Crop Irrigation Management and Water Use Impact,” grant agreement: 645642), hereafter referred to as REC SSM. This dataset includes near-surface SM measurements (3–40 cm) from the Algerri-Balaguer site (2017–2020), the Foradada site (2016–2017), and the Urgell SM field campaign, which collected SM samples from 54 locations at various times in 2015 (Fig. 1).

2.2.4. Land classification datasets

To distinguish SM under different land cover types and farmland conditions, we integrated data from SIGPAC (Geographic Information System of Agricultural Plots, <https://agricultura.gencat.cat>). SIGPAC is

Fig. 8. Chart of feature contributions in the downscaling SSM retrieval using the SHAP approach, with BG_SSM as background SSM and DF_BC as backscatter difference. Each point represents a SHAP value for a given feature and sample. The horizontal location indicates the impact on the model output (positive or negative), while the color reflects the feature value (red for high, blue for low). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

Summary of the accuracy comparison between in-situ SSM and CD-DS SSM across different sites.

Site name	R	RMSE (cm ³ /cm ³)	ubRMSE (cm ³ /cm ³)	MAE (cm ³ /cm ³)	Bias (cm ³ /cm ³)
La Cultia d'Àreu	0.55	0.063	0.041	0.047	0.044
El Boixer	0.74	0.051	0.047	0.043	-0.019
Batlliu de Sort	0.56	0.064	0.058	0.050	0.020
Bolvir	0.76	0.053	0.023	0.049	0.047
Cantallops	0.64	0.059	0.049	0.046	0.032
Garriguella	0.43	0.060	0.032	0.052	0.051
Borda Coll	0.85	0.035	0.019	0.030	0.030
Serra de Costa Ampla	0.67	0.061	0.056	0.050	-0.027
Pessonada	0.68	0.050	0.030	0.041	0.040
Clot de Les Peres	0.81	0.101	0.096	0.082	-0.003
Camí dels Nerets	0.53	0.062	0.050	0.048	0.036
Llivia	0.41	0.063	0.048	0.051	0.040
Clarella	0.66	0.066	0.056	0.054	0.036
El Miracle	0.75	0.050	0.047	0.039	0.018
Aguilar de Segarra	0.49	0.032	0.020	0.032	0.026
Ribera de Sió	0.55	0.058	0.048	0.045	0.032
Los Coscolls	0.56	0.060	0.052	0.041	0.025
Coll de Paller	0.65	0.031	0.030	0.023	0.006
Average	0.63	0.056	0.045	0.046	0.024

a geospatial database that classifies agricultural plots by land use, including cropland, pasture, forest, irrigated land, and non-agricultural areas. By integrating SIGPAC crop type and irrigation coefficient data with visual interpretation, we identified five land cover types in the study area: forest, vineyard, grassland, shrubland, and fruit tree (Fig. 3). This approach allows for a comprehensive analysis of SM variations across different land covers, strengthening the robustness of our study.

3. Method

3.1. Research framework

The primary methodology of this study is to generate high spatial resolution SSM data by downscaling the 1-km DISPATCH SSM product. The approach integrates downscaling and CD methods with ML, which learns the relationship between coarse-resolution SSM patterns and high-resolution input variables—specifically Sentinel-1 SAR and

Sentinel-2 NDVI—in order to predict fine-scale SSM. In-situ SM measurements serve as ground truth labels for model training, enabling the generation of high spatiotemporal resolution SSM products. Fig. 4 illustrates the proposed framework for generating accurate, seamless, high-resolution SSM data through the CD-DS approach. The process to produce 30 m SSM data consists of four main steps: (a) Preprocess remote sensing and in-situ datasets by converting formats, spatial alignment, and interpolating temporal data (Section 3.2); (b) Compute backscatter differences from radar signals to capture SM variations (Section 3.3); (c) Generate training data by extracting and normalizing feature values from multiple sources, followed by training ML models (Sections 3.4–3.6); (d) Validate the estimated SSM through visual verification and statistical comparison with in-situ measurements (Section 3.7).

Detailed processing steps for each stage are documented in the following sections.

3.2. Preprocessing data

In this study, datasets are converted to GeoTIFF from their original formats for consistency. VV, VH, and NDVI data are reprojected to WGS 1984 UTM Zone 31N and resampled to a 30-meter resolution via bilinear interpolation. The DISPATCH SSM is regridded from its original 1-km resolution to a 30-meter pixel size to ensure spatial alignment with the other input features. To align with the 6-day SAR imagery, non-SAR datasets with varying temporal resolutions undergo linear interpolation to match the SAR timescale.

3.3. Calculating backscatter difference

Firstly, the reflection of radar signals from the surface can be modelled as a combination of signals reflected by bare soil and those attenuated by vegetation cover (Attema and Ulaby, 1978). These two contributions can be represented as:

$$\sigma_{cover}^0 = \sigma_{veg}^0 + \gamma^2(\theta)\sigma_{soil}^0 \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma^2(\theta) = \exp[-2\tau/\cos(\theta)] \quad (2)$$

In the formula above, $\gamma^2(\theta)$ denotes the two-way transmissivity of the vegetation canopy, which varies with the incidence angle θ . The optical thickness parameter τ is influenced by the canopy's structural characteristics and water content (Gupta et al., 2013).

The spatiotemporal variations in SM are directly reflected in the changes in radar signals. Many studies have shown that radar signal differences correlate linearly with SM (Xing et al., 2022). Therefore, the

Fig. 9. Scatterplot of CD-DS SSM vs. in-situ SSM for all sites in different months.

variation in radar signals, or backscatter difference, is an indispensable variable in SM retrieval.

Temporal variations in SM are directly linked to changes in radar signals. In our study, by analyzing radar signals within the same 30×30 m grid cell and under approximately constant NDVI conditions, the impact of surface roughness is mitigated by computing the difference between radar backscatter values acquired on two different dates. For example, for a given NDVI, the minimum σ^0 value representing the driest condition is identified by analyzing all corresponding radar data

for each cell. The radar signal difference at a given cell (i, j) between any date d and the driest condition is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta\sigma_{(i,j)}^{NDVI} = \sigma_{(i,j),NDVI^d}^0 - \sigma_{(i,j),NDVI^{dry}}^0 \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{(i,j),NDVI^d}^0$ represents the backscattered signal from cell (i, j) at date d , with NDVI derived from Sentinel-2 images; $\sigma_{(i,j),NDVI^{dry}}^0$ represents the lowest backscattered signal observed under the driest conditions.

Fig. 10. Scatterplot of CD-DS SSM vs. REC SSM at Algerri-Balaguer site (first and second from left) and Foradada site (right).

Fig. 11. Scatter plot comparing CD-DS SSM with Urgell field campaign SSM across all sampling points.

However, the limited temporal coverage of the radar dataset prevents retrieving this relationship for every NDVI value. Therefore, we consider NDVI classes for the computation of $\sigma_{(ij),NDVI}^{(d_{\text{dry}})}$, using the same interval. Then, we calculate the minimum and maximum values of the NDVI images and divide them into 20 classes. In this study, we employ the VV polarization band of Sentinel-1 along with NDVI values derived from Sentinel-2 to retrieve backscatter differences. The VV band is chosen over the VH band because it exhibits greater sensitivity to soil conditions and is less affected by vegetation interference with the radar backscatter coefficient in this polarization mode (He et al., 2016). The backscatter difference is calculated by identifying the minimum VV backscatter for each NDVI class and subtracting this minimum from the VV backscatter of each pixel within the same NDVI class. Since NDVI inherently reflects vegetation seasonality, this method helps reduce vegetation-related variation and better isolate the SM signal.

3.4. Generating SSM training data

The sampling process extracts latitude and longitude coordinates from the ICGC soil survey network, retrieving corresponding values from 30-meter resolution datasets, including VV, VH, NDVI, regridded DISPATCH SSM, and backscatter difference. SSM at 5 cm depth is used as the training label. To ensure stable and balanced model training, all input features are normalized using Min-Max scaling to the (0, 1) range, addressing their differing numerical ranges. The label values, which exhibit positive skew typical of SM data, undergo logarithmic

transformation to reduce distribution bias and improve model performance. Predicted values are inverse-transformed to their original units for evaluation. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets at a 6:2:2 ratio within each in-situ station, ensuring that each station and its representative land cover and surface conditions contribute proportionally to the training and evaluation processes. This enhances model robustness and minimizes bias.

3.5. Choosing ML model

This study evaluates four ML models—Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest (RF), eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)—for SSM estimation. SVR maps data into a high-dimensional space using kernel functions (linear, polynomial, radial basis function) to capture nonlinear relationships (Drucker et al., 1997). It is configured with a radial basis function kernel, $C = 100$, $\gamma = 0.1$, and $\epsilon = 0.1$. RF improves prediction accuracy and reduces overfitting by aggregating multiple decision trees (Breiman, 2001). The model is set with 30–100 trees, a maximum depth of 15, and a minimum of 30–200 samples per leaf node, with the “sqrt” strategy for feature selection. XGBoost enhances gradient boosting by optimizing tree learning and regularization, improving computational efficiency and scalability (Chen & Guestrin, 2016). The model is configured with learning rates of 0.01–0.2, tree depths of 3–9, γ values of 0–0.2, and a minimum child weight of 1. LSTM, a recurrent neural network (RNN), captures long-term dependencies in time-series data through gated mechanisms (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997). It is trained with learning rates of 0.01–0.2, 30–200 neurons, a dropout rate of 0.2, and the Adamax optimizer for 200 epochs with a batch size of 32.

3.6. Tuning parameterization

Model performance depends heavily on input variable selection. To assess its impact, we systematically evaluate variable combinations, adjusting inputs, testing different background SSM products, and exploring alternative configurations. For hyperparameter tuning of ML models, we use Bayesian optimization to efficiently identify near-optimal settings with fewer iterations than traditional methods (Shahriari et al., 2016). This improves model performance, stability, and computational efficiency. Specifically, for each ML model, we tune hyperparameters such as neurons, learning rate, batch size, and epochs, selecting the best combination based on validation performance. To prevent overfitting, we also apply early stopping during training. Additionally, to further validate the model’s stability and reduce biases from dataset splitting, we use ten-fold cross-validation to assess model performance.

Fig. 12. Comparison of time series curves for different sites (CD-DS SSM, DISPATCH SSM, in-situ SSM and precipitation).

3.7. Validation of the estimated SSM

The validity analysis is necessary to confirm whether the SSM generated by the CD-DS ML method accurately represents true SM conditions at a 5 cm depth. This study employs three approaches: (1) comparing estimated SSM with in-situ SSM data from multiple sites, (2) analyzing time series curves to evaluate consistency between estimated and in-situ SSM, and (3) visually assessing spatial distribution consistency at the image level.

To evaluate the accuracy of each method, statistical metrics such as the correlation coefficient (R), root mean square error (RMSE), unbiased RMSE (ubRMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and bias are computed. These metrics are obtained by comparing the estimated SSM with actual SSM measurements and are defined by the following equations:

$$R = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\sum_i (SSM_{i,est} - SSM_{i,real})^2}{\sum_i (SSM_{i,est} - SSM_{i,ave})^2}} \quad (4)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{num_p} \sum_i (SSM_{i,est} - SSM_{i,real})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$ubRMSE = \sqrt{RMSE^2 - Bias^2} \quad (6)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |SSM_{i,est} - SSM_{i,real}| \quad (7)$$

$$Bias = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (SSM_{i,est} - SSM_{i,real}) \quad (8)$$

where i means the number of testing samples; $SSM_{i,est}$ and $SSM_{i,real}$ represent the predicted and real SSM for sample i , separately; and

Fig. 13. Comparison of time-series curves of CD-DS SSM, DISPATCH SSM and REC SSM at Algeria-Balaguer sites (top and center) and the Foradada site (bottom).

SSM_{i_ave} represents the mean value of all SSM estimations.

4. Result

4.1. Evaluation of background SM products

Selecting an appropriate background SSM product is essential for downscaling. Given their matching spatial and temporal resolutions, CGLS SSM and DISPATCH SSM are evaluated against in-situ measurements at a 1-km resolution for the period 2017–2018. As shown in Fig. 5, both products overestimate SSM, but DISPATCH SSM shows better accuracy, with a higher correlation ($R = 0.57$) and lower error ($RMSE = 0.07 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, $ubRMSE = 0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$). In contrast, CGLS SSM significantly overestimates SM and displays repeated values, likely due to the interpolation process used for daily resolution. The limited consistency between the two datasets can be attributed to the difference in spatial scale, as the in-situ measurements represent SM at a scale of a few meters, whereas the background SSM data is derived at a 1-km resolution.

To gain deeper insights into the temporal variations of background SSM products from January 2017 to December 2018 at Ribera de Sió, the

time-series comparison in Fig. 6 shows that both background SSM products capture SSM changes and the impact of precipitation events. However, both products overestimate SM against in-situ SSM, with CGLS SSM exhibiting greater bias. Given its superior accuracy, DISPATCH SSM was selected for further analysis.

4.2. Evaluation of downscaling ML models

By optimizing the tuning parameters with Bayesian Optimization, the training accuracy enhanced, increasing R^2 by 0.148 and reducing RMSE by $0.015 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. By comparing the performance of different ML models on the test set, as shown in Fig. 7, we find that the XGBoost model is the optimal choice among the four models. It not only performs best during training, with an accuracy of $R^2 = 0.984$ and $RMSE = 0.009 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, but also achieves high accuracy on the test set, with $R^2 = 0.933$ and $RMSE = 0.023 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Additionally, it has a more efficient running speed. Although the RF algorithm is adept at modelling complex nonlinear relationships between SSM and other environmental variables, and the deep learning-based LSTM model effectively captures temporal dependencies, both perform better than the SVR model but still fall short of XGBoost (LSTM: $R^2 = 0.864$, $RMSE = 0.032 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$; RF:

Fig. 14. Comparison of spatial distribution of CD-DS SSM and DISPATCH SSM in different subsets.

$R^2 = 0.761$, $RMSE = 0.043 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$). The SVR model has the longest runtime and the lowest accuracy ($R^2 = 0.533$, $RMSE = 0.060 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$), likely due to its limited ability to capture nonlinear relationships. Therefore, XGBoost was selected in this study for SM retrieval.

To assess the generalization of the XGBoost model, 10-fold cross-validation was performed, yielding stable results (average $R^2 = 0.961 \pm 0.0025$; $RMSE = 0.0173 \pm 0.0007 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$). SHapley Additive ex-Planations (SHAP) analysis shows that background SSM is the primary contributor, providing a strong SM baseline (Fig. 8), followed by backscatter difference and NDVI. Backscatter difference effectively reflects changes in SM, while NDVI indicates vegetation health and density, indirectly influencing moisture conditions. VV, sensitive to surface roughness and moisture, ranks next, whereas VH has the least impact due to signal attenuation by vegetation cover.

4.3. Validation of downscaled SSM on ground measurement sites

To validate the CD-DS SSM estimated using the proposed model, the in-situ SSM data from all stations in the ICGC soil measurement network between 2022 and 2024 are used for verification. Table 2 summarizes the accuracy comparison between observed and estimated SSM across different stations. The results indicate that the developed ML model successfully and efficiently retrieves SSM under all scenarios at all stations. The best performance in downscaling SSM retrieval is observed at the Borda Coll station, where the correlation coefficient (R), RMSE and ubRMSE are 0.85, 0.035 cm^3/cm^3 and 0.019 cm^3/cm^3 , respectively. The worst performance is at Llivia, with $R = 0.41$, $RMSE = 0.063 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, and $ubRMSE = 0.048 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ compared to in-situ data.

To further evaluate the model’s accuracy and seasonal stability, we

conducted monthly validation of the downscaled SSM across all sites (Fig. 9). Most months show correlation coefficients ($R > 0.5$), indicating strong agreement between predictions and observations. January and June have the highest correlations ($R = 0.81$ and 0.73), while lower values in April and August ($R = 0.53$ and 0.50) may result from vegetation-induced surface variability, as indicated by high NDVI values. RMSE ranges from 0.05 to $0.07 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, with a slightly higher RMSE ($0.07 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) in February, possibly due to precipitation-induced variability. MAE remains consistently low ($0.04\text{--}0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$), while bias fluctuates between -0.02 and $0.04 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, with minimal bias in March. Positive biases in August, September, and October ($0.04 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) suggest slight overestimation, likely due to increased surface roughness in drier conditions. These results highlight the influence of seasonal factors on model performance. High accuracy in January reflects stable winter SM with minimal agricultural activity, whereas lower accuracy in August coincides with increased vegetation, irrigation, and evaporation. Strong performance in September aligns with post-harvest stability and dry soil conditions (Traver et al., 2022).

Overall, the monthly validation results demonstrate that the proposed downscaling approach effectively captures seasonal variations in SM while maintaining high accuracy and stability.

Fig. 10 compares estimated SSM with in-situ measurements at three sites: Algerri-Balaguer3, Algerri-Balaguer4, and Foradada. Correlation coefficients range from 0.53 to 0.61, indicating a relatively strong agreement between predictions and observations. Algerri-Balaguer4 shows the lowest ubRMSE ($0.04 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$) and MAE ($0.03 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$), while Foradada has higher errors ($RMSE = 0.09 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, $MAE = 0.07 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$). This discrepancy may stem from the limited field data at Foradada and its 3-cm depth measurements, differing from the 5-cm

Fig. 15. CD-DS SSM spatial and temporal distribution of SSM during the dry (upper) and wet seasons (lower) at the Serra de Costa Ampla site ($42^{\circ}14'30''\text{N}$, $0^{\circ}51'30''\text{E}$ – $42^{\circ}11'30''\text{N}$, $0^{\circ}58'00''\text{E}$).

Fig. 16. Comparison of the spatial distribution of CD-DS SSM on the zoomed-in subset with the distribution of irrigation types in SIGPAC.

depth used for model training. These results highlight the model's robustness in capturing SM variability in Catalonia.

Furthermore, we compared the model's predictions with SM data collected during the 2015 Urgell field campaign. The study area includes irrigated forage crops (alfalfa), maize, fruit trees, and rainfed cereals. Given the 30-m resolution of CD-DS SSM, closely located sampling points within the same 30-m grid were averaged into a single value for comparison. The result (Fig. 11) shows a strong correlation ($R = 0.82$) with a ubRMSE of $0.06 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, MAE of $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$, and a model bias of $0.02 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. The model performs well in the $0.07\text{--}0.2 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ SSM range, where most data points align closely with the 1:1 line. However, some deviations at extreme values may stem from data collection conditions and spatial heterogeneity. Overall, the comparison confirms the model's strong performance.

4.4. Validation of downscaled SSM on temporal scales

To assess the temporal variability of downscaled SSM using different background fields, we compared it with in-situ SSM measurements from field stations between January 1, 2022, and January 1, 2024 (Fig. 12). The downscaled SSM products effectively capture SM dynamics and rainfall patterns, with higher SSM values primarily corresponding to major precipitation events from March to May and November to January. Conversely, lower SSM values are predominantly observed during the hot and dry season, from July to September.

Furthermore, the time-series curves of CD-DS SSM align more closely with in-situ SSM, effectively capturing SM variations following precipitation and irrigation events. At stations such as Coll de Paller, Borda Coll, La Cultia d'Areu, and Pessonada, CD-DS SSM outperforms

DISPATCH SSM by reducing overestimation, likely due to its higher spatial resolution. For example, at Borda Coll, DISPATCH SSM represents SM at a 1-km scale, while CD-DS SSM provides finer localization, yielding estimates closer to in-situ measurements. CD-DS SSM also demonstrates improved sensitivity to precipitation and irrigation events (inferred from sharp SM increases in time series without recorded rainfall). At Camí dels Nerets (March–April 2022), all datasets show an SM increase following irrigation. However, at Batlliu de Sort (March–April 2023), CD-DS SSM correctly captures the declining SM trend due to water shortage, while DISPATCH SSM shows an increase. In June 2023, during a precipitation event at El Miracle, all datasets detect a sudden SM rise.

Then, the time-series comparison at three sampling sites with REC SSM (Fig. 13) reveals sudden data gaps at certain periods. DISPATCH SSM shows the most pronounced fluctuations, with significant deviations from measured SSM on specific dates. In contrast, CD-DS SSM better aligns with observed temporal trends but exhibits slight variability compared to REC SSM, likely due to spatial heterogeneity at the 30-m scale and noise effects.

The fit between CD-DS SSM and measured SSM is slightly better at Algerri Balaguer than at Foradada, possibly because Foradada's measurements are taken at a 3-cm depth. Overall, comparisons with different in-situ datasets confirm the model's strong alignment with observed SSM, accurately capturing seasonal variations and abrupt changes following precipitation and irrigation events. This underscores its ability to reflect both gradual and rapid SM dynamics.

Fig. 17. Comparison of the spatial distribution of CD-DS SSM on the zoomed-in subset with the distribution of irrigation types in SIGPAC.

4.5. Validation of downscaled SSM at spatial scale

In the spatial distribution comparison (Fig. 14), CD-DS SSM demonstrates a clear advantage over the 1-km DISPATCH SSM by providing significantly enhanced spatial detail at 30-m resolution. While both datasets exhibit similar overall SM patterns, CD-DS SSM more effectively differentiates land cover types, capturing SM variations across vegetated mountains, croplands and forests, as well as irrigation strategies, offering a more detailed representation of spatial variability.

High-resolution SSM products reveal significant spatiotemporal variability across the study area. Fig. 15 presents a subset around the Serra de Costa Ampla site, covering an area of approximately 50 km². The SSM results show clear distinctions between the dry and wet seasons within this subset. The western part, characterized by mountainous terrain, remains notably drier throughout both seasons, while the eastern lowlands are primarily agricultural fields. During the dry season, the fields exhibit clear signs of moisture stress, which becomes significantly elevated following irrigation events. In contrast, during the wet season, SM value in agricultural areas generally remains higher.

Additionally, the retrieved SSM closely aligns with SIGPAC irrigation type maps, effectively distinguishing between rainfed and irrigated farmland. In Fig. 16, a zoomed-in view of specific subsets is presented to illustrate irrigation events captured by the CD-DS SSM. The selected SSM maps correspond to dates when irrigation activity is evident, allowing for meaningful comparison with the SIGPAC irrigation status. Under different scenarios and on different dates, the CD-DS SSM reliably differentiates irrigated from rainfed areas based on its value distribution—lower SSM values correspond to rainfed zones, while higher values indicate irrigated areas. This detailed analysis in Fig. 16 underscores the high precision and consistency of the CD-DS SSM in accurately identifying irrigation types.

5. Discussion

5.1. Main perspective of the CD-DS approach

This study addresses the challenge of low spatial resolution in SSM data by integrating change detection methods into a ML downscaling framework. By combining the characteristics of SAR and NDVI data, the research introduces a novel change-related feature—the backscatter difference—as an input to the model. This approach successfully downscales coarse-resolution background SSM data to a high-resolution 30-m scale, achieving high accuracy when compared to in-situ measurements, maintaining spatial distribution consistency, and ensuring time-series fitting.

However, uncertainties and limitations remain. First, abrupt vegetation changes, such as harvesting or burning, can cause sudden NDVI fluctuations, potentially affecting SSM retrieval accuracy. The use of fixed NDVI classification intervals may also introduce boundary errors by failing to reflect gradual vegetation changes. Second, the temporal resolution of CD-DS SSM relies on Sentinel-1 data. Since the decommissioning of Sentinel-1B in August 2022, revisit frequency has dropped to 12 days. The limited radar coverage thus constrains the monitoring of transient and seasonal SSM variations. Third, model performance is influenced by sample representativeness. The current training dataset, drawn from specific areas, may not encompass the full range of crop types or climatic conditions, limiting spatial generalization. Fourth, although our downscaling strategy directly models SSM at 30-m resolution using in-situ observations as labels, combining multiple auxiliary variables and coarse-resolution background SSM, spatial mismatch between pixel-based estimates and point-based measurements remains a challenge (Meng et al., 2024). SSM estimation also depends on the quality and relevance of input features. We selected VV, VH, backscatter difference, NDVI, and DISPATCH SSM for their strong physical link to SM, fine spatiotemporal resolution, and high data availability. However,

relevant variables such as precipitation, temperature, and topography were excluded due to limited spatial resolution or data access.

For future work, the model's generalization and spatial transferability could be improved by incorporating more diverse training samples from different climatic zones and crop types. Also, integrating other physically relevant variables could enhance the model's sensitivity to environmental changes and its ability to capture transient moisture dynamics. Lastly, future satellite missions will enable the fusion of L-band SAR with other sensor data, enhancing spatiotemporal coverage for continuous, field-scale SSM monitoring.

5.2. Evaluation of preprocessing approaches

In this study, Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2, originally at 10 m resolution, were resampled to 30 m, which introduced additional errors and noise. Although Sentinel-2 has a nominal 5-day revisit cycle, persistent cloud cover reduced the effective observation frequency to more than 10 days. In contrast, Sentinel-1 SAR imagery provided consistent 6-day observations. To synchronize both datasets, linear interpolation was applied to generate NDVI values from Sentinel-2 imagery at 6-day intervals. While this ensures temporal continuity, it introduces uncertainty, particularly during rapid phenological changes or external disturbances such as agricultural activities or natural events. Longer gaps (e.g., long-term cloud cover during the rainy season) increase the likelihood of inaccurate NDVI estimates, thus reducing model accuracy and reliability.

To maximize observation frequency and sample size, both ascending and descending orbit Sentinel-1 data were utilized. While variations in incidence angle can introduce backscatter discrepancies and geometric distortions, our study area predominantly comprises flat or gently sloping terrain, minimizing significant geometric errors such as layover and shadow. Also, our proposed ML algorithm is trained to learn and accommodate systematic biases arising from different orbit directions (ascending vs. descending) and residual incidence angle variations, thereby enhancing the model's generalization capability and improving SM estimation accuracy. The integration of data from complementary observation geometries also enables the capture of more comprehensive information regarding surface characteristics, further reinforcing the reliability of the estimation results (Li and Yan, 2024). The complementary observation geometries help capture additional surface information, mitigating surface roughness and vegetation effects, ultimately refining SM retrieval (Ma et al., 2020).

5.3. Contribution of in-situ SSM to the performance of CD-DS SSM

Since in-situ SSM provides the most reliable SM measurements compared to remote sensing-derived data (Arabi et al., 2020), its integration is important for enhancing model accuracy. Leveraging these ground-based observations not only strengthens calibration and validation but also plays a key role in refining downscaling approaches. Furthermore, increasing the number of field stations would significantly enhance the estimation of SSM across the entire Catalonia region. Currently, ICGC measurement stations are mainly concentrated in northern and central Catalonia, with limited coverage in the southern and southeastern coastal regions, where water scarcity is more severe. Expanding station distribution across diverse locations is essential to improve land surface representativeness. The ICGC network was originally established to monitor vineyards at various altitudes due to their economic importance, resulting in a concentration of stations in vineyard-dominated farmland. In addition, we acknowledge that the observed variability in model performance across different validation sites (as shown in Table 2) may partly be attributed to spatial representativeness errors arising from land cover heterogeneity within the 30 m satellite pixel. Such mismatches, as also discussed by Peng et al. (2025), likely contribute to site-specific variations in model performance. To investigate this, we analyzed land cover at sites with varied

performance. For example, sites such as Ribera de Sió (Fig. S1) and Clot de Les Peres (Fig. S2) exhibit significant land cover heterogeneity within the 30 m pixel, which corresponds with their below-average model performance. This diversity means a single-point sensor may not accurately represent the pixel-wide average SM. Conversely, the Borda Coll site, with its more homogeneous vineyard land cover (Fig. S3), achieved a higher accuracy ($R = 0.85$), likely due to a better match between the point measurement and the pixel-scale estimation. These observations are consistent with previous findings by Peng et al. (2025), and further underscore the need to consider and quantify site-specific land surface heterogeneity to better account for representativeness errors.

5.4. Consistent spatial distribution between CD-DS SSM and SIGPAC irrigation status

Spatial consistency verification using SIGPAC data shows that CD-DS SSM aligns well with shapefile boundaries, effectively distinguishing irrigated and rainfed areas. However, accuracy is influenced by factors such as irrigation timing, farmer practices, and irrigation methods.

For instance, in Fig. 17 (upper), some irrigated plots exhibit high CD-DS SSM values, while adjacent irrigated fields show lower levels, likely due to differences in irrigation application. In Fig. 17 (lower), CD-DS accurately differentiates a semicircular irrigated plot from a narrow rainfed strip, but surrounding irrigated fields display significantly lower SSM values, suggesting variations in irrigation timing or technique. Additionally, crops like vineyards, which are more drought-tolerant and rely on drip irrigation, further influence observed SM levels.

6. Conclusion

Coarse-resolution SSM products struggle to capture rapid SM changes at the agricultural field scale, necessitating a high-resolution alternative. This study develops an ML framework integrating change detection and downscaling to estimate SSM at a 30-m spatial resolution, an improvement from the original 1-km scale. By leveraging SAR, NDVI, and DISPATCH background SSM, this approach achieves precise, timely, and low-cost SM mapping. Training data were compiled from various Catalonia regions, and multiple ML models were tested to identify the most accurate for estimating CD-DS SSM. The XGBoost model performed best, achieving an R^2 of 0.933 and RMSE of $0.023 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ on the test set. Validation against ground measurements showed an average R of 0.63, a ubRMSE of $0.045 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$. Notably, backscatter difference was the second most important variable in the ML model. Comparison with a 2015 field campaign (54 sites) yielded an R value of 0.82 and an RMSE of $0.06 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$.

The CD-DS SSM effectively captures field-scale SM dynamics, essential for monitoring irrigation, drought and agricultural impacts. Temporal analysis revealed consistency with in-situ data, capturing seasonal trends and abrupt changes after precipitation and irrigation. January and June showed the highest correlations ($R = 0.81$ and 0.73 , respectively), while RMSE generally remained between 0.05 and $0.07 \text{ cm}^3/\text{cm}^3$ throughout the months. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of SSM well-aligned with irrigation maps, differentiating irrigated (higher SSM) and rainfed (lower SSM) zones. These findings highlight the CD-DS SSM's ability to detect local SM conditions, aiding agricultural monitoring and farm management. Given the large data volume, more efficient computational methods are being explored for real-time SSM processing across Catalonia.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zihao Wang: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Qi Gao:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Michele Crosetto:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Maria Jose**

Escorihuela: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2025.104702>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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